

GFRP Connectors as Shear Friction Reinforcement for Concrete Composite Elements

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ABSTRACT

The junction of composite concrete elements is subjected to horizontal shear. Therefore, shear connectors are utilized at the interface to maintain their integrity. This study examines the performance of glass fiber-reinforced polymer (GFRP) reinforcement as shear friction reinforcement at concrete cold joints. A total of three specimens, each made up of two L-shaped blocks cast at two stages to provide the intended shear plane condition, were tested under monotonic shear load, in which two were reinforced with GFRP connectors and one with steel stirrups. The results demonstrated that GFRP connectors can withstand friction shear in a way similar to their steel counterparts.

KEYWORDS

Friction shear; composite element; cold joint, shear connectors.

INTRODUCTION

Composite members have been utilized to build structures that are smaller, shallower, and lighter (Loov & Patnaik, 1994). Additionally, incorporating composite components has shown efficiency in accelerating the construction process, thereby minimizing total costs. A composite member might be a steel or precast reinforced concrete (RC) girder combined with a concrete slab. The flange or cast-in-place slab and the girder must function as a single unit in a composite beam. The advantages of adopting composite members can only be utilized if shear caused by external loads at the interface can be counteracted without producing separation between the two distinct elements. Such separation can be avoided by multiple techniques, the most common of which is the reinforcement across the shear contact surface.

Steel reinforcement at the interface of concrete composite components has been thoroughly researched and recognized by the current design codes ACI 318-19 (ACI, 2019), CSA A23.3-19 (CSA 2019a), and CSA S6-19 (CSA 2019b). Steel, on the other hand, is prone to corrosion in harsh weather conditions, particularly when de-icing salt is used. To overcome the corrosion concern, the noncorrosive glass fiber-reinforced polymer (GFRP) reinforcement has demonstrated its effectiveness as a substitute for the traditional steel under flexural and shear loads (El-Sayed et al., 2005). Birkeland and Birkeland (1966), Badoux and Hulsbos (1967), Mast (1968), Hofbeck et al. (1969), Loov and Patnaik (1994), ACI 318-19 (ACI, 2019), and CSA A23.3-19 (CSA, 2019a) were all built on the assumption that shear reinforcement yields at failure. Such an assumption contradicts GFRP behavior, which fails due to rupture (Connor & Kim, 2016) without any yielding plateau. This mode of failure makes the available design guidelines of steel-RC members inappropriate on FRP.

Current GFRP design codes and guidelines, such as CSA S806-12 (CSA, 2021), ACI 440.11-22 (ACI, 2022) and ACI 440.1R-15 (ACI, 2015), have no design equations to predict the friction shear at cold joint interface due to the lack of experiments. In addition, the effect of different parameters, including reinforcement ratio and concrete strength, were not studied by Connor and Kim (2016). Therefore, no design models are developed to predict the interface-shear capacity when FRP connectors are used. On the other hand, the CSA S6-19 (CSA, 2019b) permits the use of FRP as a friction shear reinforcement with a 0.44 % minimum reinforcement ratio crossing the shear plane.

This paper is a part of ongoing research program composed of 29 specimens addressing a large number of key parameters as an attempt to fill this gap. The experimental results of two large-scale GFRP-RC specimens consisted of two L-shaped blocks placed at different stages are presented. The two specimens were compared with one steel-RC specimen with the same properties. The main tested parameter was the reinforcement ratio crossing the shear plane.

Experimental Program

Material Properties

Normal strength, ready-mixed concrete with a design strength of 30 MPa was used for all specimens. However, 100 × 200 mm cylinder samples were tested on the test day to determine the actual compressive strength according to ASTM C39-20. Closed stirrups were used as shear connectors for all specimens. The mechanical properties of the sand-coated GFRP bent bars, as provided by the manufacturer, are listed in Table 1. Figure 1 shows the used GFRP bent bars (stirrups).

Table 1: Mechanical properties of GFRP bent bars

Bar Type	Nominal Diameter (mm)	Bar Area (mm ²)	Modulus of Elasticity (GPa)	Tensile Strength (MPa)	Strain at Ultimate
10M (Bent bars)	9.5	72	49.3	1,125	2.28%

Figure 1: GFRP sand-coated stirrup connector

Test Specimens

Table 2 shows the test matrix for this study. A total of three specimens, each made up of two L-shaped blocks cast at two stages to provide the cold joint interface condition, were constructed, and tested to failure. The specimens had dimensions of 1,050 mm in length, 600 mm in width, and 300 mm in thickness, giving a 400 × 300 mm shear plane. A 25-mm gap was provided between the two blocks to accommodate slippage, as shown in Figure 2. The first block was poured horizontally with the intended reinforcement projected from the interface placed perpendicularly to the shear plane, which simulates the common practice. The concrete surface was left as is with no further treatment. After seven days, the second block was placed and connected to the first block through the shear connectors. Figure 3 shows the casting stages. Each block was reinforced with steel; 15M in the longitudinal direction and 10M stirrups to strengthen the specimen away from the shear plane. This ensures the specimen failure to coincide with the shear plane. Two specimens were reinforced with GFRP connectors, whereas steel connectors were used for the third one. All connectors were size 10M (9.5 or 11.3-mm diameter for GFRP and steel stirrups, respectively). The specimens were tested under monotonic load through a push-off test. This test was used due to the ability to induce pure shear with no moment along the interface.

Table 2: Detailed test specimens

Specimen ID	Connector Type	Number of Connectors	Reinforcement Area (mm ²)	Reinforcement Ratio (%)	Concrete Strength (MPa)
S2	Steel	2	400	0.33	33
G1	GFRP	1	144	0.12	
G2		2	288	0.24	

Figure 2: Test specimen, (a) Specimen geometry, and (b) Typical L-block geometry

Figure 3: Construction of test specimens, (a) Reinforcement cages before casting, and (b) After casting the first L-block

Test setup and procedure

As shown in Figure 4, the specimens were placed vertically on a concrete block to be tested under a monotonic vertical load applied by a hydraulic actuator with a displacement rate of 0.1 mm/min. Two linear variable displacement transducers (LVDTs) were attached on each side of the specimen to track the relative displacement of the block along the shear plane until failure. LVDTs were attached 10 mm away from the shear plane to avoid any instrumentation damage after the crack formation. In addition, one PI-gauge was provided on each side of the specimen to measure the crack width. Moreover, strain gauges were attached on the shear connectors to monitor the strain throughout the test.

Figure 4: Test setup

Results and Discussion

Experimental Results

Due to the difference in reinforcement ratio and material used for shear connectors, the failure mode was depicted in terms of load versus relative slippage and load versus strain as shown in Figures 5 and 6, respectively. In addition, the ultimate loads are presented in Table 3. Results revealed that the specimens reinforced with steel or GFRP connectors had approximately the same capacity. This demonstrates the applicability of using GFRP stirrups as friction shear reinforcement at the cold-jointed concrete interface. Despite the lower modulus of elasticity of GFRP compared with steel, the three specimens reached an ultimate load of 398, 399, and 404 kN for specimens G1, G2, and S2, respectively. These results demonstrate that the friction shear is predominantly controlled by the concrete. The ultimate load was associated with a crack formation at the interface. Generally, the behaviour of the specimen can be divided into two phases: pre-cracking and post-cracking.

Table 3: Push-off tests

Specimen	Ultimate load (kN)
S2	404
G1	398
G2	399

Each specimen had a different mode of failure, as illustrated in Figure 7. Specimen G1 had a sudden load drop to 125 kN immediately after the crack initiation. After that, the load was transferred and started to be carried by the reinforcement in addition to the concrete contribution resulting from the surface roughness or aggregate interlocking. The load tended to slightly increase to 161 kN before the GFRP stirrup rapture. Specimen G2 had a similar behaviour throughout the test but with a different post-peak load. The load dropped to 191 kN, then increased to 261 kN before the rapture of the GFRP connectors. This reveals the significance of increasing the reinforcement ratio crossing the interface, in which increasing the reinforcement ratio from 0.12 to 0.24% resulted in approximately 37% increase in the post-peak load. For both specimens, no additional loading was attained after cracking. However, the connectors in both specimens exhibited more than 8,000 $\mu\epsilon$ prior rapture. Specimen S2 had a similar cracking load to the GFRP ones. Yet, it had a different post-peak behaviour due to the difference in material characteristics. The load dropped gradually reaching 252 kN and remained constant with insignificant load gain due to the reinforcement yielding.

Load-slip behaviour was monitored through the attached LVDTs on the specimens. At the peak load, relative slip was 0.20 mm for specimens G1 and G2 and 0.33 mm for specimen S2. These slippages are higher than the recommended slippage of 0.13 mm by Hanson (1960) and Saemann and Washa (1964). For G1 and G2, the relative slippage increased immediately to 0.65 and 0.45 mm, respectively, and continued to increase with a very slight increase the load. However, a lower increasing rate of slippage for G2 was observed, which can be attributed to the dowel mechanism contributed by the additional stirrup in this specimen.

Figure 5: Load-slip relationship for test specimens

Figure 6: Load-strain relationship for test specimens

Figure 7: Mode of failure of test specimens: (a) G1, (b) G2, and (c) S2

Conclusions

In this experiment, two GFRP-RC specimens were cast, tested under push-off test, and compared with one steel-RC counterpart. Reinforcement ratios were 0.12 and 0.24 % for the GFRP-RC specimens, whereas this ratio was 0.33 % for the steel-RC one. The main objective was to evaluate the performance of GFRP stirrups under friction shear. The following concluding remarks are drawn based on the discussion and the analysis of the results:

- GFRP connectors or dowel bars performed well in resisting friction shear stresses.
- The lower modulus of elasticity and the anisotropic characteristics of GFRP bars, with the tested reinforcement ratio, seemed to not affect the capacity compared to the counterpart steel-RC specimen since the overall capacity was resulted from the concrete.
- Failure of the GFRP-RC specimens occurred immediately after the crack of the specimen.
- Reinforcement area crossing the shear plane had a major role in controlling the post-peak behavior. Increasing the dowel reinforcement resulted in more gradual and lower drop in the load after crack initiation. In addition, higher loads were achieved before the GFRP rupture.

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CONFLICT OF INTEREST

The authors declare that they have no conflicts of interest associated with the work presented in this paper.

DATA AVAILABILITY

Data on which this paper is based is available from the authors upon reasonable request.

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